

ISLAMIC CORPORATE FINANCE, FINANCIAL MARKETS, AND INSTITUTIONS

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***Abstract:** Formally launched in the 1970s, the Islamic finance industry has deep roots in Islamic law (Sharia) and many implications for modern finance. The industry has grown much faster than conventional finance over the past four decades, and it is now worth an estimated US\$1.6 trillion.¹ Moreover, while 80% of Islamic finance is concentrated in the Middle East, North Africa, East Asia, and the Pacific, it is active in 59 countries across the globe. From a pragmatic perspective, in the context of international banking and capital markets, Islamic finance could now be considered mainstream, as it is widely used by both firms and governments in developed and emerging economies. Despite its development, academic researchers have been slow to embrace Islamic finance as a topic for empirical and theoretical analysis.*

***Keywords:** Islamic finance, Islamic economics, Islamic banking, Sharia-compliance, Sukuk, Islamic bonds, Sharia boards*

Introduction

This special issue of the Journal of Corporate Finance (JCF) aims to overcome this academic inertia by showcasing well-developed Islamic finance research of interest to the general reader of corporate finance and that has practical implications for corporate managers.² The papers in this special issue explore two main aspects of Islamic finance that help to reduce the cost of Islamic capital in banking and in the debt (bond) and equity markets. The issues examined, while focusing on unique aspects of Islamic finance, very much depend on mainstream behavioral finance and

corporate governance theories. In this review, I group the papers under two broad themes: investor tastes and governance.

This special issue of the JCF presents papers considered for the 2nd Islamic Banking and Finance Research Conference held at King Fahd University of Petroleum & Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran, Saudi Arabia on November 19, 2017. The papers underwent a double blind-refereeing process, and then were invited for publication in this special issue where they underwent the JCF's review process. While a number of excellent papers on broader Islamic finance issues were included in the conference program, the papers ultimately accepted for this special issue were those that had clear and well-defined implications for those interested in corporate finance-related topics.

Investor tastes and the Cost of Capital

According to the efficient market hypothesis, social or religious norms should not impact returns for three reasons. First, if we assume that these norms are linked to priced risk factors, then stock prices should already reflect the information they contain. Second, if we assume that these norms are linked to unpriced risk factors, then arbitrage forces will exploit any mispricing they cause. Third, if we assume that these norms are not linked to any legitimate risk factor then, on average, they should not impact stock returns.

However, social or religious norms may affect returns for the subgroup of investors who strictly follow them. Specifically, filtering investments based on norms imposes a cost on investors by narrowing the universe of potential investments and potentially leading to less diversification. At the same time, investors may gain utility by investing in a way that matches their values and beliefs. For example, investors are willing to pay a premium for socially responsible investments but ask for a discount to invest in "sin" stocks (Bollen, 2006). If this is true, then one would expect ethical investments to underperform, while sin stocks would outperform on a risk-adjusted basis. Such mispricing, from a market efficiency perspective, may not be arbitrated away if social norms also influence arbitrageurs. Shafron (2018-this issue) and

Alhomaidi et al. (2018-this issue) address the impact of investor preferences on bonds and equities, respectively.

Shafron (2018-this issue) uses investor preferences for Islamic bonds (*Sukuk*) to test whether investor tastes affect asset pricing, and hence the cost of capital (specifically, the cost of borrowing). The author argues that Islamic finance provides a more objective and cleaner setting compared to studies on investor preference for socially responsible investments. Socially responsible investments are multifaceted constructs that comprise various attributes that investors may not view equally. Additionally, investors may determine the assets that satisfy these preferences with error. This is not the case with preferences for Islamic investments because investors can objectively determine the features of an Islamic investment and the assets that have those features.

Specifically, Shafron (2018-this issue) uses Malaysian bond data from 2005 to 2013 to examine the yield difference between Islamic and conventional bonds. The main regression uses the coupon rate at the time of issuance to proxy for yield and regresses that coupon rate on an identification variable for Islamic bonds, along with a host of issuer and issuance controls. The regression results show that the yield on Islamic bonds is lower than that of conventional bonds by almost 50 to 75 basis points.

In addition to reporting results for all issuers, the study runs separate regressions for issuers of both types of bonds. By using dual issuers (those that issue both conventional and Islamic bonds) the author controls for the issuer's characteristics that could drive the results, and thus addresses endogeneity issues and self-selection bias due to unobservable variables related to issuers. Although using dual issuers provides a cleaner test, it reduces the sample size significantly, as the sample does not contain many dual issuers.

The results for dual issuers are similar to those of the full sample.

Additionally, the author acknowledges that the lower yield on Islamic bonds may stem from the inherent differential in risk rather than in taste. To disentangle the impact of taste, the author adds a variable to measure the macro demand for Islamic

bonds relative to conventional bonds, which measures the general taste for Islamic bonds. This variable is interacted with the Islamic bond identification variable. The coefficient on this variable is negative, indicating that Islamic bond yields are lower than that of conventional bonds. Interestingly, the coefficient on the identification variable for Islamic bonds becomes insignificant when adding the interaction term. This indicates that the yield differential between Islamic and conventional bonds is mainly due to taste.

In addition to highlighting the role of investor tastes in bonds markets, the study contributes to the scarce literature on Islamic bonds by building the most comprehensive empirical model to determine the yield of Islamic bonds. It also extends the literature on investor tastes by using the bond market for the test, as most existing studies use equity markets.

On equity, Alhomaidi et al. (2018-this issue) use stock return data from Saudi Arabia between 2002 and 2015 to examine how preferences for Islamic stocks affect several factors that can cause their returns to differ from those on conventional stocks. The most unique aspect of using data from Saudi Arabia is the fact that individual investors dominate the Saudi stock market. These investors are generally religious (as compared with institutional investors). This setting serves two purposes: it helps identify Islamic stocks as those that match investor tastes, and it allows the authors to classify conventional stocks as being neglected by religious individual investors. Thus, compared to the literature on socially responsible stocks and on sin stocks, the Islamic finance context in this study allows the researchers to examine both categories of stocks at the same time for the same set of investors.

Empirical evidence in the literature shows that socially responsible investors are willing to pay more for socially responsible stocks but require a premium to invest in sin stocks. The same logic applies in the context of investing in *Sharia*-compliant stocks. Similar to socially responsible investors, Muslim investors are willing to pay more for *Sharia*-compliant stocks relative to conventional stocks with similar risk.

Numerous empirical studies on the performance of *Sharia*-compliant investments report conflicting results. Many studies try to assess the risk-reward profile of

Sharia-compliant stocks relative to a broader universe. Studies show evidence of outperformance (Hussein and Omran, 2005; Hayat and Kraeusl, 2011; Rubio et al., 2012), underperformance (Mansor and Bhatti, 2011; Hoepner et al., 2011), or insignificant abnormal returns (Hassan and Girard, 2010; Ashraf and Nazeeruddin, 2014). Other studies show asymmetric performance based on market conditions. Hussein (2004), Merdad et al. (2010), Al-Khazali et al. (2014), and Ho et al. (2014) show that *Sharia*-compliant investments outperform in bear markets but underperform in bull markets.

The mixed results on the performance of *Sharia*-compliant portfolios can be explained from different perspectives. First, some studies use samples from non-Muslim majority countries. If *Sharia*-compliant stocks have a unique risk-return profile due to the impact of social norms, then a significant difference should be correlated with the proportion of Muslims who observe the norms and act upon them.

Therefore, we should not expect a significant difference between *Sharia*-compliant stocks and the broad benchmark, if the market used in the analysis does not have a significant proportion of Muslim participants. Second, it is possible to have a wide pool of *Sharia*-compliant stocks across industries, which enable investors to build a portfolio closer to the efficient portfolio. Third, the mixed results may relate to a missing relevant variable that correlates to preference for *Sharia* compliance.

Alhomaidi et al. (2018-this issue) take the analysis one step further to relate the preference for *Sharia*-compliant stocks to several characteristics that affect returns. In particular, the authors show that because Islamic stocks enjoy better recognition than do conventional stocks in Saudi Arabia, they have a broader investor base, are more liquid, have lower idiosyncratic risk, exhibit greater integration with local and global macroeconomic factors, and have higher systematic turnover. The authors showcase a battery of methods to measure these factors and control for several firm-level factors in their regressions.

In addition to contributing to our understanding of how Islamic stocks can differ from conventional stocks in a Muslim market, this study also contributes to the general literature on investors' beliefs and stock returns. Although the literature on social

investing and sin stocks explains *why* returns on these types of stocks are different, it does not explain *how* those differences in returns occur. Alhomaidi et al., provides evidence that differences in beliefs affect returns through affecting the risk and liquidity profile of recognized and neglected stocks. Their results can be extended to understand the sources of return differences in sin and socially responsible stocks.

Another paper in this issue looks at how investor tastes affect banking relationships. Beck et al. (2018-this issue) ask whether firms select geographically proximate banks and how bank orientation (Islamic vs.

Conventional) plays a role in that decision. Using a database that lists Turkish firms' primary bank relationships, the authors match 7,659 firms with 9,546 bank branches and calculates the distance between the firm and the bank branch. The results show that the likelihood that a firm would select a bank is significantly determined by the proximity of the bank. In particular, if the bank is 10 kilometers away from the firm, the likelihood that the firm selects the bank decreases by 7.5 percentage points.

Interestingly, the significant impact of distance in the firm-bank relationship is weaker if the bank is Islamic and much weaker if the firm resides in regions that are more likely to be religious. The authors use voting for conservative political parties and survey results on trust in religious institutions to classify regions according to political beliefs and religious sentiments.

These findings indicate that firms that choose to deal with Islamic banks do so regardless of distance, especially if the firm is more likely to be of the conservative type that would choose to deal with Islamic banks over conventional banks. To provide more evidence, the authors run the same regression on a subsample of firms that deal with both Islamic and conventional banks and find that the type of bank does not affect distance. Thus, only firms that choose Islamic banks intentionally ignore distance. Other findings in the paper show that Islamic banks are usually further from their client-firms than conventional banks, even after controlling for bank characteristics, such as size, government ownership, and foreign ownership. Thus, although distance impacts the firm-bank relationship, Islamic banks can still

enjoy client relationships without having to be closer to clients, indicating loyalty among Islamic banks' clients.

Beck et al. (2018-this issue) adds to the existing literature by aiming to show how the religious attitude of Islamic banks' clients create loyalty to the bank, regardless of its performance. This in turn may give more pricing power to the bank. Abedifar, Molyneux, and Tarazi (2013) argue that Islamic banks may be under less pressure to perform, if clients are loyal due to religious responsibility, which may in turn increase the manager's risk taking. Weill (2011) explores the possibility that the demand for Islamic banking by religious clients is inelastic, thus giving the bank more power over pricing. He shows that Islamic banks do not have power over pricing and charge the same or less than conventional banks to reduce the incentives to default. In a more recent study, Baele, Farooq, and Ongena (2014) examine individual loan records in Pakistan and show that Islamic loans charge 2% higher rates than conventional loans, after controlling for key factors. From another perspective, loyalty among Islamic bank clients can enhance stability. Farooq and Zaheer (2015) use weekly deposit data for all banks in Pakistan to assess withdrawal risk and the impact on lending during the 2008 Global Financial Crisis. Their results show that after controlling for bank characteristics, Islamic banks had lower withdrawals, attracted more deposits, disbursed more loans, and had less sensitivity in lending to deposits during the crisis.

Bitar and Tarazi (2018- this issue) show how loyalty to Islamic banks reduces the need to address information asymmetry through signaling. The authors begin by arguing that in stronger creditor protection environments, banks increase their equity capital to signal their safety. Using data on 793 banks (including 113 Islamic banks) from 24 countries, the authors show that Islamic banks operating in more religious countries (based on Muslim population) do not need to respond to creditor protection by signaling their quality through increasing equity. This is because in more religious environments, debtors (depositors) are captive and will deal with the Islamic bank, regardless. This may not be true in less- religious countries. In such countries, and especially if the Islamic bank has high market power, Islamic banks behave like conventional banks and increase equity in response to stronger creditor protection.

Governance and Cost of Capital

Several differences between Islamic and conventional banks can result in governance issues that are specific to Islamic banking. For example, Islamic banks are asset-based and their operations hinge on risk sharing, as opposed to conventional banks, which are debt-based and operate on the method of risk transfer (Mejia et al., 2014). For example, the investment account holder (depositor) in an Islamic bank shares with the bank the risk and return resulting from investing the deposited amount. Farooq et al. (2015) point out the profit-loss sharing in investment accounts means that such accounts are not pure deposits (or liabilities). At the same time, they are not considered equity because they are redeemable in nature. However, in practice, banks consider them as a liability as they earn competitive rates, and thus investment account holders have cash flow rights but no control rights.

Due to risk sharing, depositors in Islamic banks might have an incentive to monitor the bank, but the bank, in its equity holders' best interests, may have less incentive to monitor borrowers (Beck et al., 2013). This complex relationship between depositors and equity holders makes monitoring by depositors costlier, especially in presence of managerial discretion and absence of a standard way to measure investment performance (Safieddine, 2009). In addition, Islamic banks have more complex operations that involve buying and selling real assets, maintaining an inventory of assets, and involving third parties that trade real assets with the bank, which can reduce efficiency and increase transaction costs and taxes (Ariss, 2010; Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt, and Merrouche, 2013). Additionally, *Sharia* restrictions can increase asset concentration and lead to higher credit or market risk. With a limited set of *Sharia*-compliant hedging and risk management tools, the risk profile of Islamic banks can differ from that of conventional banks (Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt, and Merrouche, 2013; Elnahass, Izzeldin, and Abdelsalam, 2014).

However, the above agency and operating costs can be mitigated by market forces (withdrawal risk), governance (board of directors and the *Sharia* board), and limited monitoring by depositors. Abedifar, Molyneux, and Tarazi (2013) argue that the threat of deposit withdrawal if returns are not competitive with conventional banking

mitigates the high cost of monitoring by depositors. This withdrawal risk makes banks more disciplined and alert to risk in order to protect equity holders who would otherwise absorb some of the losses.

Mollah and Zaman (2015) address the difference between Islamic and conventional banks in terms of governance. According to their study, Islamic banks have a similar board size when compared to conventional banks, but twice as many independent directors. Their empirical findings indicate that board size and independence have a negative impact on an Islamic bank's performance. Mollah et al. (2016) build a corporate governance index of 12 components, including board size, board independence, and CEO duality, to compare Islamic banks to conventional banks across different countries. They report a higher impact of better governance on Islamic banks' performance relative to conventional banks.

Additionally, they show that better governance in Islamic banks enables risk taking.

In addition to regular boards, Islamic financial institutions have *Sharia* boards that play an additional governance role (Mollah and Zaman, 2015; Elnahass, Izzeldin, and Abdelsalam, 2014). The main role of *Sharia* boards is to approve financial products from a *Sharia* perspective, but they can also assume a monitoring responsibility.

Mollah and Zaman (2015) argue that *Sharia* boards may restrict managers' excessive risk taking, overleveraging, and aggressive lending, and can add an additional layer of governance. Mollah and Zaman (2015) provide empirical evidence that *Sharia* boards have a positive impact on an Islamic bank's performance, especially when they have supervisory roles. Safieddine (2009) surveys 40 GCC Islamic financial institutions on governance-related issues including board effectiveness, *Sharia* board effectiveness, rights of investment account holders, auditing, financial disclosure, and reporting. He finds that better governed Islamic financial institutions are smaller, more profitable, have higher valuations, and outperform weakly governed Islamic financial institutions.

Safiullah and Shamsuddin (2018-this issue) focus on the impact of *Sharia* boards on the efficiency of Islamic banks. The authors acknowledge that relative to

conventional banks, Islamic banks operate under different product portfolios, production technology, customer bases, and institutional conditions. The authors first compare the efficiency of Islamic and conventional banks without assuming a common efficiency frontier. In particular, the authors match each Islamic bank with its conventional counterpart by country and size and then use a stochastic production meta-frontier framework that estimates the group-specific frontiers. The results indicate that Islamic banks are more cost efficient, but less profit efficient than conventional banks. This result holds when controlling for the differences in risks. The authors examine the impact of *Sharia* boards on cost and profit efficiency and show that the reputation and academic qualifications of *Sharia* board members enhance cost and profit efficiency for Islamic banks.

Interestingly, a larger *Sharia* board enhances profit efficiency although it increases cost inefficiency. This may indicate that smaller boards are more effective than larger boards.

The major value of a *Sharia* board is the control of *Sharia* risk, which is the risk that a transaction or a product is not conforming with *Sharia*. Basiruddin and Ahmed (2018) show how effective governance can reduce *Sharia* risk in Malaysian and Indonesian Islamic banks between 2007 and 2017. They measure *Sharia* risk by the existence and magnitude of *Sharia* non-compliant income. The results show that smaller boards, independent directors, financial expertise of *Sharia* advisors, and frequency of *Sharia* committee meetings reduce *Sharia* risk.

Sharia boards also receive criticism. Ünal (2011) shows the high concentration and close network of *Sharia* board membership, as the top 10 *Sharia* scholars hold 39% of all board positions, while the top 20 hold more than 50% of all board positions. Alman (2012) argues that such high concentration in *Sharia* board membership reduces monitoring ability and effectiveness. Additionally, reputation effects and network effects can influence the hiring and compensation of *Sharia* board members. Hayat, Butter, and Kock (2013) show that the market for *Sharia* certification is quite monopolistic, with nearly 20 *Sharia* scholars controlling more

than half the market, with the top 3 scholars being members of around 80 *Sharia* boards and earning an estimated US\$ 4.5 million in fees per year.

While such concentration may increase the cost to obtain a *Sharia* opinion, it can reduce the cost of capital through reputation. Godlewski et al. (2016) show that the reputation of *Sharia* scholars who approve the issuance of *Sukuk* increases announcement returns for the stocks of the *Sukuk* issuer. Abdul Halim et al. (2018-this issue) provide more direct evidence on the importance of a *Sharia* advisor's reputation by examining a sample of 3,462 Malaysian Islamic bond tranches issued between 2001 and 2014. They show that the reputation of *Sharia* advisors lowers the spread on Islamic bonds at the time of issuance after including a host of issuer and issuance controls. Due to the significant *Sharia* risk in Islamic bond issuances, reputable *Sharia* advisors lower the risk since they will not compromise their reputational capital by approving *Sharia*-questionable issuances.

The results are robust to the possibility that high quality issuers naturally select reputable *Sharia* advisors. The authors addressed the endogeneity issue by using instruments for the reputation and by using propensity score matching. For a cleaner test, the authors use difference-in-difference methods to show that when a reputable *Sharia* advisor joins a standard-setting board (which the authors consider as an external shock), the impact on the spread is negative. Additionally, the authors show that switching from low- to high-reputation *Sharia* advisors leads to a lower spread.

Although several of the control variables are standard in the literature, the authors include controls that are unique to Islamic bonds, namely the use of a special purpose vehicle (SPV) and the structure of the Islamic bond. Using SPVs protects the financed asset if the issuer went bankrupt, and thus reduces the risk, while structuring the bond as debt-like is less risky than structuring the bond as equity-like because the latter does not necessarily depend on a stable cash flow stream. Interestingly, the regression outcome is contrary to the expected effect of these factors on spreads, which encourages a more careful look at Islamic bond features.

Conclusion

This special issue is a reaction to the scant rigorous work in Islamic finance and the limited scope of existing analysis, despite several relevant and interesting research questions. If anything, the existing literature calls for additional research that uses more data and better identification. In many cases, modern Islamic financial practices can provide better tests of how religion impacts economics. Islamic finance can produce a direct link with an unambiguous direction from religion-induced culture to economic outcomes. Researchers can adopt a battery of identification strategies for this purpose, such as using exogenous changes in regulations, running comparative analysis with conventional counterparts, or testing reactions to exogenous shocks.

The papers in this issue provide excellent examples of the described empirical rigor. They portray how Islamic finance research can fit within the vast literature of conventional finance. The main themes in these papers capitalize on the uniqueness of Islamic finance in terms of user loyalty and the role of *Sharia* scholars in governance. The papers show that these aspects can affect the cost of capital and efficiency in financial markets and institutions. It is important to mention that these papers also bring a unique contribution to the conventional finance literature by utilizing unique contexts in Islamic finance that conventional finance cannot provide.

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